

Impact of Work-Life Balance on Employees' Turnover and Turnover Intentions: An Empirical Study on Multinational Corporations in Bangladesh

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Abstract: Work-life balance (WLB) is one of the burning issues in the business arenas to ensure the sustainable steady performance of the organizations. Work-life balance influences the turnover and turnover intentions of the employees which are the indicators of employees' job satisfaction. In this rapid growing world, majority of the business sectors are now being occupied by giant Multinational Corporations, hence it is very challenging for the organizations to compete in this competitive world without satisfied motivated employees. The aim of this study is to find the impact of work-life balance on employees' turnover and turnover intentions of multinational corporations working in Bangladesh. The research is basically based on primary data collected from different multinational corporations from different industries such as telecom, tobacco, fashion, consumer goods. To test the hypotheses different statistical tools such as One sample t test, ANOVA test, Correlation were used based on survey data. Linear regression analysis executed to establish a model to find out the impact of various dependent variables over independent variable. From the analysis of the survey it was found that poor work life balance leads to higher employees turnover and turnover intentions and proper work-life balance of employees has a positive effect over the performance of the organizations.

Key Words: Employee Turnover, Turnover intention, Organizational Performance, Work-life balance, HR policies

1. Introduction

In theory, work-life balance is a comfortable state of stability between an employee's key priorities of their employment position and their private standard of living. Most psychologists would agree that the demands of an employee's career should not devastate their own ability to enjoy a gratifying personal life outside his/her career. Employee turnover, or staff turnover, is a measurement of how many employees that retires or quit from an organization (James Wilkinson, 2014). One of the main focuses of this study is to find whether there is any relationship between employee turnover and employee work life balance. The process of job turnover described as job dissatisfaction is the first step, followed by the intention to leave, which finally, in some cases, can result in actual turnover (Mobley et al. 412; Bannister & Griffith 437).

It is very tough to pursue a well-balanced work-life. Career demand always contradicts with one's own personal life. It is important to be satisfied in personal life to perform

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better in professional life. According to *Hyatt (2016)*, “Those who feel satisfied with their personal lives are more satisfied with their careers and perform better.”

A work-family conflict has a great impact on employee turnover and turnover intention. Human resources play an important role for the development of intellectual property in organization which is totally impossible to imitate. Both work and family responsibilities have been increased in the recent times. This study focused on relevant variables regarding work-life balance; identify important factors and also provide recommendations that will add value to the multinational corporations to help their employees cope up with work-life balance.

Bangladesh is a fast growing developing country. The economy of this country has been growing rapidly and now it has started competing in a global basis. Many Multinational organizations have entered in this growing economy and also some local organizations expanded their operations beyond the national boundary. Over last 5 years GDP growth rate of Bangladesh has risen from 6.01 (2013) to 7.05 (2016) (*Monetary Policy Statement 2016, P-04*). Literacy rate increased from 59.72% (2013) to 70% (2015) over last four years (bdnews24.com, 2015). Human resources of Bangladesh is now becoming more globally competent due to advanced education system and also focus on training and development of employees by corporations.

This study topic is especially significant because in more than a few situations, it is intensifying for work-family conflict on employees in different organizations in Bangladesh. According to recent researches, more female employees are joining into the labor force (Hossain & Tisdell, 2005). Longer working hour is creating more obstacles for employees to balance work and family life for dual income families (Alam et al., 2011). In addition, family as an important institution in Bangladeshi culture is constantly generating a particular demand to create and look after families (Crozier & Davies, 2006). Lastly, organizations in Bangladesh have not adopted with family-friendly policies properly yet (Hossain, Sarker & Afroze, 2012; Alam et al, 2011). The increased number of dual career families with no organizational support for employees to balance work and family role is creating constant pressures on the researchers and managers to explore work-family conflict issues in Bangladesh. Considering the prevalent workforce demography and employee expectations, organizations of Bangladesh must admit the pressing problem of work-family conflict as well as develop solutions to solve this issue.

2. Review of Literature

2.1 Employee Work-life Balance

Work-life balance has become a major issue for both employee and employer, lack of balance between work and non-work activities is related to reduced psychological and physical wellbeing an example of this is working during the weekends which has been linked to stress and emotional exhaustion for employees, (Hughes and Bozionelos, 2007).

Bell, Rajendran & Theiler (2012) found that work-life conflict has negative career consequences, such as lack of future promotions, less productivity and also job exit. If employees believe that use of work benefits related work-life balance may cause any

chances of career progression or cause them to be viewed negatively at work, then they were unlikely to use available benefits, which may cause them to experience work-life conflict.

Herlin (2010) investigated the relationship between the availability and the use of work-family balance policies offered by organizations and family-supportive organizational perception (FSOP), work-to-family conflict, employee retention and affective commitment, job satisfaction, turnover intention and psychological strain. Saif, Malik and Awan (2011) examined the relationship of employee work satisfaction (job satisfaction) and impact of work life balance (WLB) on it in Pakistan. They had verified a relationship of work life conflict and job satisfaction among Pakistani employees and revealed a negative relationship between the variables.

Work-life and work-family issues have been the subject of rhetorical, policy and research thoughtfulness in different developing and developed countries including Australia. Many studies from 2000 onwards have observed that has been so hard for employees to manage their family commitments; work-life conflict Skinner (2013). There is substantial evidence that the cost of poor work-life interaction on individuals, families and society as a whole is high. Chima et al (2011) examined the extent to which Work Life Balance policies and practices are a reality for employees in banking sector. The study suggested an urgent need to communicate clearly about the Work Life Balance policies and practices to its employees, to raise awareness further and improve the knowledge and understanding of relevant policies.

Shujat et al (2011) studied impact of work-life balance on employee job satisfaction in private banking sector of Pakistan. In their study they considered several factors such as gender, age, managerial position and tenure of job to reach a conclusion whether work-life balance have impact on employee performance. Abbas et al (2009) found in their study that work pressure/stress is negatively correlated with job satisfaction in both private company LMK Resources (A renowned petroleum technology company) and public company National Database and Registration Authority (NADRA). They found that job satisfaction is significantly negatively correlated with work to family intervention and family to work intervention. Saleem et al. (2013) studied the same issue but in another state in Pakistan. In their study they found, job stress has very low collision on job satisfaction of employees in banking sector of Bahawalpur. They also found that work anxiety also has weak relation with employee job performance in Pakistan.

2.2 Employee Turnover and Turnover Intention

Victoria Jagun (2015) studied reasons behind employee turnover within the Irish hospitality sector. She found that Work-life balance was a critical issue. When it is contradicted by work-related commitments, stress is inevitable. Hence it causes turnover intention of employees. In every industry, work-life balance is an important element that usually determines employee satisfaction.

Shamim et al (2014) studied job dissatisfaction and turnover of employees in corporate sector in Bangladesh. According to their study the process of job turnover can be defined as job dissatisfaction is the first step, followed by intention to leave, which finally, can

result in actual turnover. They tried to identify the experiential evidences of turnover in three different situations. They are i) being dissatisfied with the previous job, ii) availability of job in the market and iii) (search for) better alternative job as well as identifying the factors affecting job dissatisfaction. According to their study important factors that affect job dissatisfaction are work environment & administration of the organization, supervisors & working hours and Job security.

Alam et al (2014) made a study on Influencing Factors Responsible for Job Turnover: Bangladesh Perspective. They tried to identify the factors which lead to job turnover in Bangladesh. They found that the main factors of the employee turnover are compensation structure, management & organizational structure, nature of work and supervision and income and career path.

2.3 Impact of Work-life balance on Employee Turnover and Turnover intentions

According to Schilling (2014) turnover intention is backed by work interference with personal life to a great extent. Based on her study, conflict with personal life with work life may cause serious damage to mental health and sometimes employees go through high stress that may cause his/her turnover.

Chiang et al (2008) made a study on “*The Effect of Work-Life Balance Policies on Women Employees Turnover*” on Japanese working woman. He found that the majority of women quit their jobs when they get married or give birth to a child. After a certain period, they re-enter the labor market when their children have grown up. The study found out only child-care system is not enough for the women after their childbirth. Work-life conflict could happen to employees at each stage in life especially early stage of the life of their children. According to Cordero et al (2009), work-family conflicts influence employees’ dissatisfaction of job and turnover intention. The motivation to quit from the organization is positively related with work-family conflicts. The solution for work-family conflict needs to introduce work-life balance that is described as a self-perceived and satisfactory integration of time, family care responsibilities fulfillment and work related responsibilities fulfillment. Therefore, a balanced work environment strongly suggested to satisfy work and family needs.

Rashid et al (2013) conducted a research on work-life balance and stress with the turnover of employees in Pakistan. The purpose of their study was to find out the relationship of the work-life balance and stress with employee turnover. The results of the study showed that there is a relationship between work-life balance and stress with the employee turnover. Khairunneezam (2011) studied the relationship between perceived work-life balance satisfaction of academics in Malaysian public higher education institutions and their intentions to leave the organization. The study outcomes indicated that alleged work-life balance satisfaction was correlated negatively with employee turnover intention in the organization among academics. The results of the simple arbitration analysis indicated that job satisfaction and organizational obligation are fractional mediators for the relationship between work-life balance and intention to leave.

Ghayyur & Jamal (2012) studied the work-family conflicts in relationship with turnover intention. It was discovered that work-family conflicts exist and possess positive

relationship towards turnover intention. Work-family conflicts influence employees' turnover intention in both banking and pharmaceutical organizations.

3. Research Design and Methodology

3.1 Objectives of the Research

General Objective

In line with the research question, primary objective of this research was to examine the relationship between impact of work-life balance on employee turnover as well as turnover intention of employees in multinationals corporations in Bangladesh.

Specific Objectives

The specific objectives of this study were:

- detecting number of hours that employees devote in office in different industries as well as in different level of the career to measure their available time for family
- analyzing the point of views of employees about work-life balance and their productivity
- finding obstacles that employees face to maintain family commitment linking work-life balance and turnover intention of employees

3.2 Hypotheses

The study tested the following hypotheses:

Ha₁= Work life balance has a negative relation with turnover intention of employees

Ha₂= Good work-life balance of employees has a positive effect on organizational performance and success

Ha₃= Working hours and less time for family negatively affects employee work-life balance

Ha₄= Woman employees are not able to balance their work-life than men.

3.3 Sources of data

Employees of multinational corporations are the primary source of data for this research. The data were collected from 232 employees from different offices of 15 multinational corporations in Dhaka city.

The primary data were collected through face to face interview as well as online questionnaire survey using Google form.

3.4 Sampling and sample size

In this study, convenience sampling (non-probability technique) was the main sampling technique as it was the most suitable sampling technique based on the time and resources the researcher had. Convenience sampling chooses samples from the population based on their convenient approachability and closeness to the researcher. In all forms of research,

the ideal situation is to test the entire population but in most of the cases, it is not accurate to include every individual given the population is so large.

3.5 Methods of data analysis

To execute the data analysis, SPSS 16.0 was used for the descriptive analysis of the respondents (profile of respondents), one sample t-test was conducted for hypothesis testing and factor analysis was performed to extract the variables and highly correlated variables been identified. Correlation matrix was also used to identify the correlation among different variables.

The main software used to analyze the data was SPSS along with supporting software like MS Excel, Google doc. In SPSS v16.0 statistical tools like ‘One sample t test’, ‘One-way ANOVA test’, ‘Univariate ANOVA test’, ‘Pearson’s Correlation test’ was used based on survey data. Linear regression analysis was used to establish a regression line so that it can be found that the impact of different variables on independent variable.

4. Findings and analysis

4.1 Descriptive statistics of respondents

Table 1: Age and gender of respondents

		Gender	
		Female	Male
Age	20-35	40	80
	36-45	22	72
	45+	0	18
	Total	62	170

(Source: Survey data-2017)

In this study there were 232 respondents from different Multinational Corporations in different industries in Bangladesh. Among them 62 respondents are female (27%) and 170 respondents are male about 73%. Most of the respondents belong to 20-35 age group about 120 respondents and only 18 respondents are from 45+ age group.

Table 2: Time devoted to organizations by respondents in different industries

		How many hours in a day do you normally work?		
		7-8 hours	9-10 hours	11-12 hours
		Row N %	Row N %	Row N %
Type of Industry	Consumer goods	12.5%	43.8%	43.8%
	Fashion	.0%	92.0%	8.0%
	Others	43.5%	43.5%	13.0%
	Telecommunication	.0%	75.0%	25.0%
	Tobacco	12.0%	60.0%	28.0%

(Source: Survey data-2017)

This table illustrates the relationship between employees working hour based on industry practice. According to the survey it can be found that in consumer goods industry, Fashion, Telecommunication and Tobacco industry more than 85% of employees have to work for more or equal to 9 hours a day, surprisingly 43.5% of employees from consumer goods related MNCs work more than 10 hours a day. But, 43.5% of employees works less or equal 8 hours a day in other industries such as education and immigration, information technology, outsource based businesses etc.

According to the survey, 33% of employees are single and 67% of employees are married. Among the married employees of multinational corporations 66% of employees are dual career couple.

Figure 1: Major obstacles for WLB

(Source: Survey data-2017)

The pie chart demonstrates key complications for balancing employee work-life balance. According to the survey, majority of employees think that long working hours (more than 8 hours a day) is the major obstacle to balance employee work-life (49%).

Table 3: Employee response on research related scale based questions

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
Employee Satisfaction regarding working hour of the company	12.90%	46.24%	16.13%	19.35%	5.37%
Available time for family of employees	19.35%	47.31%	17.20%	13.97%	2.15%
Ability to balance work-life	13.98%	32.25%	31.18%	19.35%	3.22%
Employee perspective on good work-life balance and its impact on organizational success	0	0	2.15%	32.25%	65.59%
Employee perspective on impact of good work-life balance and employee performance	0	0	2.15%	39.78%	58.06%
Impact of work-life balance on turnover decision	3.23%	15.05%	29.03%	35.48%	17.21%
Work-life balance and employee turnover intention	6.45%	13.98%	13.98%	31.18%	34.41%

(Source: Survey data-2017)

*'Employee Satisfaction regarding working hour of the company' is based on regular working hour regardless of 8 hours a day

The report shows that 46.24% of employees are dissatisfied with their working hour where only 5.37% employees are highly satisfied with that. Based on time availability of employees 47.31% of employees are dissatisfied with their time availability for their family. But more than half of the employees strongly believe that good work-life balance of employees can have a great impact on employee performance as well as organizational success. Finally, about one third of the respondents agree with the statement that work life balance of employees is one of the major reasons for employee turnover of employees as well as turnover intentions.

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics of scale data

	N	Mean	Mode	Std. Deviation	Variance
Employee Satisfaction regarding working hour	232	2.581	2	1.09666	1.203
Available time for family of employees	232	2.323	2	1.01254	1.025
Ability to balance work-life	232	2.656	3	1.04772	1.098
Employee perspective on good work-life balance and its impact on organizational success and effectiveness	232	4.634	5	.52719	.278
Employee perspective on impact of good work-life balance and employee performance	232	4.559	5	.54098	.293
Impact of work-life balance on turnover decision	232	3.484	4	1.04894	1.100
Work-life balance and employee turnover intention	232	3.731	4	1.25230	1.568
Valid N (list wise)	232				

(source: Survey data-2017)

The table describes the descriptive statistics of 7 major survey related questions. Mean of “Employee satisfaction regarding working hour” is 2.58, whereas Std. Deviation 1.10; for the data of “Available time for family of employees” the mean is 2.3226, mode is 1.01; Variance is 1.03 from which it can be concluded that both these data bear more or less similar response of respondents. Mode of ability of employees to balance their work-life is 3 with an average of 2.66 where variance is 1.10 and 1.05 as the Std. Deviation. Most of the respondents strongly agree that employee work-life balance has a positive impact on Organizational performance and employee performance as well.

According to the employees, impact of work-life balance on employees’ turnover of previous job and current intention has same mode value which is 4. Their mean are 3.48 and 3.73 consecutively with the variance of 1.10 and 1.57

4.2 Hypothesis, result and discussion

Hypothesis 1:

Work life balance has a negative relation with turnover intention of employees

Table 5: Pearson's correlation between work-life balance and employee turnover intention

Correlations			
		Do you feel that you are able to balance your work life properly?	Do you think present work-life balance will be a major reason if you leave your current job?
Do you feel that you are able to balance your work life properly?	Pearson Correlation	1	-.618**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	232	232
Do you think present work-life balance will be a major reason if you leave your current job?	Pearson Correlation	-.618**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	232	232

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

According to the Pearson correlation it can be found that the correlation between conditions of current work-life balance and employee turnover intention is -.618 which means they are negatively correlated. Significance level was set at .05 which means 1 percent only. In this correlation test significance level or P value is .000 which represents that the test is highly significant.

Table 6: Model Summary of hypothesis test 1

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics	
					R Square Change	Sig. F Change
1	.618 ^a	.382	.375	.98989	.382	.000

Predictors: (Constant), do you feel that you are able to balance your work life properly?

Model summary specifies multiple models in a single table. It describes number of the model being reported in the respective test. According to the model summary following things can be summarized:

According to the table, value of R is .618 and R-Square is .328 that means the dependent variable (employee turnover intention) can be explained by independent variable (Work life balance of employees) by 32.8% which is in sense pretty high as only a single factor can explain about one third of the reason behind the change in dependent variable. Adjusting with extra unimportant predictors it can be found that adjusted R square is .375 that refers dependency of dependent variable (employee turnover intention) can be explained by the independent variable (Work life balance of employees) by 37.5%. Std. Error of the estimate is .98989. According to the study results the significance of the study is .000 which represents that the study is highly significant.

Table 7: ANOVA of hypothesis test 1

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	55.110	1	55.110	56.241	.000 ^a
	Residual	89.170	231	.980		
	Total	144.280	232			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Do you feel that you are able to balance your work life properly?

b. Dependent Variable: Do you think present work-life balance will be a major reason if you leave your current job?

From the table it can be observed that the variation to the relationship between dependent and independent variable is 55.110 and in residual sum of square is 89.170. On the other hand degree of freedom is about 231. Residual mean square is $170/92 = .980$. In this test Value of F is 56.241 having a ratio of more than 1 which represents that null hypothesis is not true.

So, Work life balance of employees is negatively correlation with employee turnover intention.

Table 8: Coefficients of hypothesis test 1

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	5.693	.281		20.258	.000	5.135	6.251
	Do you feel that you are able to balance your work life properly?	-.739	.099	-.618	-7.499	.000	-.934	-.543

a. Dependent Variable: Do you think present work-life balance will be a major reason if you leave your current job?

About .281 Standard error is associated with this coefficient table. Value of constant 'a' is 5.693 and b_1 is '-.739'

So the regression line will be $Y = 5.693 + (-.739) X_1$

Here,

Y= Employee turnover intention (Dependent variable)

X_1 = Employee work-life balance (Independent variable)

In summary it can be concluded that using this test it can be said that null hypothesis has been rejected.

Hypothesis 2:

Good work-life balance of employees has a positive effect on employee performance

Table 9: Correlation between work-life balance and employee performance

Correlations				
		Do you think that if employees have good work-life balance the organization will be more effective and successful?	Do you feel that you are able to balance your work life properly?	Do you think that good work-life balance has a positive effect on your productivity?
Do you think that if employees have good work-life balance the organization will be more effective and successful?	Pearson Correlation	1	.183	.458**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.079	.000
	N	232	232	232
Do you feel that you are able to balance your work life properly?	Pearson Correlation	.183	1	.094
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.079		.371
	N	232	232	232
Do you think that good work-life balance has a positive effect on your productivity?	Pearson Correlation	.458**	.094	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.371	
	N	232	232	232

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Pearson correlation suggests that the correlation between conditions of organizational performance and employee work-life balance is 0.183 which is a weak uphill (positive) linear relationship, correlation between employee work-life balance and impact of work-life balance on employee performance is .094 which means they are not much correlated and lastly correlation between organizational performance and employee performance is .458 which represents that they have a moderate uphill (positive) relationship. In this correlation test significance level or P values is 0.79 which represents that the test is nearly significant, Organizational performance and employee performance is .000 that represents that the test is highly significant.

Table 10: Model summary for hypothesis test 2

Model Summary ^b						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics	
					R Square Change	Sig. F Change
1	.479 ^a	.229	.212	.46792	.229	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Do you think that good work-life balance has a positive effect on your productivity?, Do you feel that you are able to balance your work life properly?

b. Dependent Variable: Do you think that if employees have good work-life balance the organization will be more effective and successful?

Model summary shows that significance level of the study is .000 which is more than standard .05 that means the study result is highly significant. Value of R is .479 and R-Square is .229; so, the dependent variable (organizational performance) can be explained

by independent variable (Employee work-life balance, impact of work-life balance on employee performance) by 22.9% which is tolerable enough. Adjusted R square is .212 that refers dependency of dependent variable (organizational performance) can be explained by the independent variable (Employee work-life balance, impact of work-life balance on employee performance) by 21.2%; besides std. Error of the estimate is .46792; According to the study results the significance of the study is .000 which represents that the study is highly significant.

Table 11: ANOVA for Hypothesis test 2

	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	5.864	2	2.932	13.391	.000a
	Residual	19.706	229	.219		
	Total	25.570	232			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Do you think that good work-life balance has a positive effect on your productivity?, Do you feel that you are able to balance your work life properly?

b. Dependent Variable: Do you think that if employees have good work-life balance the organization will be more effective and successful?

(Source: Survey data-2017)

Sum of squares is of the regression analysis 5.864 and in residual sum of square is 19.706; here degree of freedom of the regression is 2. Significance is .000 which ensures that there is no error in the test. So it is statistically the test is significant and null hypothesis is rejected. That means, alternative hypothesis is accepted.

So, from the hypothesis testing, it can be concluded that, Good work-life balance of employees has a positive effect on employee performance.

Hypothesis 3:

Working hours and less time for family negatively affects employee work-life balance

Table 12: Coefficient for Hypothesis test 3

	Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	2.47	.423		5.84	.000	1.631	3.310
	Do you feel that you are able to balance your work life properly?	.071	.047	.141	1.52	.132	-.022	.164
	Do you think that good work-life balance has a positive effect on your productivity?	.433	.091	.444	4.78	.000	.253	.613

a. Dependent Variable: Do you think that if employees have good work-life balance the organization will be more effective and successful?

From the Coefficient table about .423 standard errors is associated with this study, value of constant 'a' is 5.693 and b_1 is $-.739$; so the regression line will be $Y=2.47+ (.071) X_1+ (.433)X_2$

Y= Organizational Success (Dependent variable)

X_1 = Employee work-life balance (Independent variable)

X_2 = Impact of work-life balance on employee performance

In summary it can be concluded that using this test it can be said that null hypothesis has been rejected and alternative hypothesis "Good work-life balance of employees has a positive effect on employee performance" is accepted.

Table 13: Correlation test for hypothesis test 3

Correlations				
		Are you satisfied with your working hour in your organization?	Do you get enough time for your family?	Do you feel that you are able to balance your work life properly?
Are you satisfied with your working hour in your organization?	Pearson Correlation	1	.701**	.554**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	232	232	232
Do you get enough time for your family?	Pearson Correlation	.701**	1	.649**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	232	232	232
Do you feel that you are able to balance your work life properly?	Pearson Correlation	.554**	.649**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	232	232	232

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Based on the study from Pearson's correlation it can be found that the correlation between working hour and time with family is 0.701 which represents that they have a strong (positive) linear relationship, correlation between employees' time with family and work-life balance is about .649 which means they have A moderate uphill (positive) relationship and lastly correlation between working hour and work-life balance is .554 which represents that they have a moderate uphill (positive) relationship. Significance level was set at .05 which means 5 percent only. In this correlation test significance level or P values working hour and time with family is .000 which represents that the test is highly significant, employees' time with family and work-life balance is .000 and finally employees' time with family and work-life balance is also .000 that represents that the test is highly significant.

Table 14: Model summary for hypothesis test 3

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.664a	.440	.428	.79240

a. Predictors: (Constant), Do you get enough time for your family?, Are you satisfied with your working hour in your organization?

This table specifies multiple models in a single table. According to the table, value of R is .664 and R-Square is .440 that means the dependent variable (employee work-life balance) can be explained by independent variable (Employee working hour and employees' time for family) by 44% which is tolerable enough. On the other hand, adjusted R-square is .428 and std. Error of the estimate is .79240

According to the study results the significance of the study is .000 which represents that the study is highly significant.

Table 15: ANOVA for hypothesis test 3

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	44.478	2	22.239	35.418	.000a
	Residual	56.511	229	.628		
	Total	100.989	232			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Do you get enough time for your family?, Are you satisfied with your working hour in your organization?

b. Dependent Variable: Do you feel that you are able to balance your work life properly?

According to the ANOVA Table it can be summarized that Sum of squares is of the regression analysis 44.478 and in residual sum of square is 56.511. Degree of freedom of the regression is 2.

“Mean Square” represents the average deviation of degree of freedom of regression. It is the ratio between sum of squares and df. Here, Mean square (Regression) = Sum of squares is 22.239 Mean square (Residual) = Sum of squares/df .628 Value of F is 35.418 having a ratio nearly 1 which represents that null hypothesis is not true where significant level is .000 which ensures that there is no error in the test. So statistically the test is significant and null hypothesis is rejected. That means, alternative hypothesis is accepted.

So, from the hypothesis testing, it can be concluded that, Work life balance of employees has a correlated with employee turnover intention negatively.

Table 16: Coefficiency for hypothesis test 3

Model		Coefficients				
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.944	.224		4.216	.000
	Are you satisfied with your working hour in your organization?	.187	.106	.196	1.770	.080
	Do you get enough time for your family?	.530	.114	.512	4.630	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Do you feel that you are able to balance your work life properly?

Based on coefficient table standard error is .224, value of constant 'a' is .944, b_1 is .187 and b_2 is .530 So the regression line will be $Y = .944 + (.187)X_1 + (.530)X_2$

Here,

Y= Employee work-life balance (Dependent variable)

X_1 = Daily working hour (Independent variable)

X_2 = Employees' time for family

In summary it can be concluded that using this test it can be said that null hypothesis has been rejected and alternative hypothesis "Working hours and less time for family negatively affects employee work-life balance" is accepted.

Hypothesis 4:

Woman employees are not able to balance their work-life than men.

Table 17: Test between subjects effects for hypothesis 4

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects					
Dependent Variable: Do you feel that you are able to balance your work life properly?					
Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	.020 ^a	1	.020	.018	.894
Intercept	518.730	1	518.730	467.512	.000
gender	.020	1	.020	.018	.894
Error	100.969	230	1.110		
Total	757.000	232			
Corrected Total	100.989	231			

a. R Squared = .000 (Adjusted R Squared = -.011)

From this data it can be seen that Sum of square of the relation between number of weekends of employees and employees' satisfaction with their work-life is .020 with degree of freedom of 1. The mean square of this test is 518.730 with the F value of .018.

The significance level was set .05 or 5% but the significance level of the study is .894 which is too high. So, our null hypothesis will be accepted and alternative hypothesis will be rejected.

So, based on the Univariate ANOVA test it can be concluded that Gender of employees has no effect on employees work-life balance.

Conclusion

From the analysis of this research it can be said that employee work-life balance has a great effect on employee turnover and turnover intention of multinational corporations along with other reasons behind employee turnover. Work-life balance not only has impact on employee satisfaction but also correlated with employee performance and organizational productivity. From this research it was found that employees of multinational corporations are suffering much to balance their work-life and ultimately they have a strong intention of moving from their respective organization if he/she gets proper benefits to move. Finally it was found that long working hour, compulsory overtime, traveling duration to office; less time to stay with family are major factors that obstruct employees to balance their work-life. Organizations are not taking many initiatives to help their employees balance their work-life. Even at present many multinational corporations are suffering from high employee turnover which leads them to lose valuable human resources created by them.

Recommendations

Based on the overall study, following recommendations can be provided to multinational corporations to help employees balance their work-life.

- a) Working hours of employees should be monitored based on job description of employees
- b) Based on the nature of jobs, organization can establish flexible work hours to their employees group to group or person to person
- c) At the end of the day money can be a major motivator to motivate employees. Overtime payments can be a major motivator to employees which might counter balance employees' dissatisfaction with work-life.
- d) Childcare system for dual career couple can be a good solution to help employees balance their work-life as well as increase employee performance. Organization should follow the labor law properly regarding this issue.
- e) Career development opportunity should be introduced and executed properly in order to motivate employees to work-hard
- f) Organizations should have psychologist to help their employees cope up with work-life conflict
- g) Proper stress management system should be introduced so that organizations can help their employees deal with work stress and work pressure

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